

Venice's macroalgae-derived active material for aqueous, organic, and solid-state supercapacitors

Ahmad Bagheri,^{a,b} Somayeh Taghavi,^c Sebastiano Bellani,^{d*} Pejman Salimi,^{e,f} Hossein Beydaghi,^d Jaya-Kumar Panda,^d Marilena Isabella Zappia,^d Valentina Mastronardi,^d Agnese Gamberini,^d Sanjay Balkrishna Thorat,^d Matteo Abruzzese,^d Lea Pasquale,^g Mirko Prato,^g Michela Signoretto,^h Xinliang Feng,^{b,i} and Francesco Bonaccorso ^{a,d*}

^a Graphene Lab, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, via Morego 30, 16163 Genoa, Italy

^b Center for Advancing Electronics Dresden (cfaed) & Faculty of Chemistry and Food Chemistry, Technische Universität Dresden, 01062 Dresden, Germany

^c Faculty of Chemistry, University of Mazandaran, 47416-95447, Babolsar, Iran

^d BeDimensional S.p.A., Lungotorrente Secca 30R, 16163 Genoa, Italy

^e Analytical and Circular Chemistry (ACC), Hasselt University, Hasselt, Belgium

^f Institute for Materials Research (imo-imomec), Hasselt University, Hasselt, Belgium

^g Materials Characterization Facility, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Via Morego 30, 16163 Genova, Italy

^h CATMAT Lab, Department of Molecular Sciences and Nanosystems, Ca' Foscari University Venice and INSTM Consortium, RU of Venice, Via Torino 155, 30172, Venezia Mestre, Italy

ⁱ Max Planck Institute of Microstructure Physics, Weinberg 2, 06120 Halle, Germany

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1 **Abstract**

2 In this study, self-doped porous activated biochar derived from Venice lagoon's *Sargassum* brown
3 macroalgae (ABS) has been successfully prepared through thermochemical carbonization (pyrolysis)
4 followed by CO₂ physical activation and used as electrodes for supercapacitor (SC) applications. The
5 ABS exhibits a remarkable specific surface area of 821 m² g⁻¹ and heteroatoms (N, O, and S) doping,
6 both key features to attain high-performance carbon-based SC electrodes. The electrochemical
7 performances of ABS-based SCs were assessed in three different electrolytes. Two are aqueous (*i.e.*,
8 1 M H₂SO₄ and 8 M NaNO₃), while the third one is the prototypical organic, namely 1 M TEABF₄
9 in acetonitrile. In these three electrolytes, the ABS-based electrodes exhibited specific capacitance
10 values (C_g) of 109.5, 79.0, and 64.3 F g⁻¹, respectively, at a current density of 0.1 A g⁻¹. The capacitive
11 performance resulted in SC energy densities of 3.45 Wh kg⁻¹ at 22.5 W kg⁻¹, 6.3 Wh kg⁻¹ at 36.1 W
12 kg⁻¹, and 12.4 Wh kg⁻¹ at 57.4 W kg⁻¹ and maximum power densities of 147, 222, and 378 kW kg⁻¹ in
13 the acidic, quasi-neutral aqueous electrolyte and organic electrolyte, respectively. The ABS
14 electrodes were used to realize a flexible solid-state SC based on the sulfonated polyether ether ketone
15 (SPEEK):functionalized niobium disulfide flakes (f-NbS₂) composite membrane. The flexible solid-
16 state SC displayed a remarkable 97% C_g retention even under various mechanical stresses, including
17 bending up to 1000 times and folding angles up to 180°, while keeping a Coulombic efficiency above
18 98%. This study reveals ABS as a promising sustainable source of active materials for SCs. The
19 remarkable performance of ABS-based SCs can be attributed to their multi-scale porosity, heteroatom
20 doping, and enhanced surface wettability, providing abundant active sites for charge accumulation,
21 and efficient electrolyte diffusion, thus highlighting its potential as a sustainable solution for energy
22 storage applications.

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27 **1. Introduction**

28 Sustainable energy storage and conversion technologies must be developed to meet rising energy
29 consumption while tackling climate change, environmental pollution, and biodiversity loss [1–3]. In
30 this context, supercapacitors (SCs) represent electrochemical energy storage systems that combine
31 the advantages of traditional capacitors and batteries by storing energy through electrostatic double-
32 layer capacitance and faradaic pseudocapacitance mechanisms [4–6]. With excellent rate capability,
33 *i.e.*, specific power (P_s) exceeding 10 kW kg^{-1} and long cycle life (up to millions of charge/discharge
34 -CD- cycles regardless of the depth of discharge), SCs outperform common battery technologies in
35 terms of round trip efficiency, longevity (*e.g.*, 20 years lifespan), and power densities. These
36 distinguishable features make SCs a compelling choice to efficiently and rapidly match the energy
37 demand, as well as to control the ramp up or down of the energy supplied by renewable technologies
38 in distributed (decentralized) renewable energy systems [7,8]. Furthermore, SCs operate efficiently
39 within a wide temperature range, *i.e.*, from $-40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, making them adaptable to/reliable in
40 extreme environments, *e.g.*, Arctic and deserts [9,10]. The SCs are commonly classified into three
41 main categories: electrical double-layer capacitors (EDLCs), pseudocapacitors, and hybrid SCs
42 (HSCs). Commercial SCs are mainly EDLCs based on high-surface carbon electrodes, which are
43 charged/discharged *via* ion adsorption/de-adsorption processes at the electrode-electrolyte interfaces
44 [10–12]. Activated carbon (AC), carbon nanotubes, and graphene have been widely used as active
45 materials for EDCL electrodes due to the combination of high electrical conductivity, large specific
46 surface area, and excellent chemical stability [5,13–15]. Even though AC still represents the most
47 economically viable active material choice amongst the aforementioned materials, marketable
48 products are commonly derived from fossil fuel precursors, increasing the cost (up to $\$5000\text{-}100000$
49 per kWh) and environmental impact of EDLCs [16]. Recently, the use of biomasses to produce AC,
50 *e.g.*, by upcycling waste materials, has been considered a suitable cost-effective strategy that
51 preserves the ecological balance. Examples of biological precursors for AC are rice husk [17], silk
52 cocoon [18], and algae [19]. Specifically, Algae, unlike land plants, can form massive populations in

53 coastal areas on all continents, but also off-shore in tanks, ropes, and other supports in marine systems,
54 *e.g.*, offshore wind parks [20,21]. They also have the ability to thrive in various aquatic environments,
55 including salt water, spurring seaweed farming that does not rely on energy-intensive farming
56 practices and does not compete for freshwater resources, resulting in the production of “truly green”
57 biomasses [22]. The accumulation of a large amount of proteins and lipids within their cellular
58 biomass is the source of N and S heteroatoms [23], which, in turn, can be used to produce heteroatom-
59 doped biochar through pyrolysis processes. During pyrolysis, these biomasses convert to heteroatom
60 as dopants into the carbon matrix without the need for extra chemical reagents [24]. Heteroatoms like
61 N, O, S, and P efficiently enhance the electrical conductivity and wettability of algae-derived biochar
62 [25]. Heteroatom insertion primarily occurs at the outer region of the carbon sheets, while the internal
63 region undergoes a process called localized crystallization [26], resulting in an ordered structure. This
64 ordered structure significantly enhances porosity, which is crucial for energy storage applications
65 [27]. Activation techniques, including chemical or physical activations and template-assisted
66 methods, can be used to increase the specific surface area (up to $\sim 3000 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and porosity (even up
67 to $>1 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$) of biochars [27,28]. More in detail, high-temperature physical activation can break
68 crosslinks between carbon sheets, resulting in the formation of free carbon layers that are conductive
69 and incorporate heteroatoms [29]. The heating process preserves the original morphology of carbon,
70 while gases escape, forming pores and channels [30]. Chemical activation using chemical etching
71 agents, *e.g.*, ZnCl_2 , KOH , and HNO_3 , leads to porous carbons with high specific surface area and
72 highly developed pore structure [29,31]. Furthermore, physical activation methods, involving steam
73 [30], carbon dioxide (CO_2) [26], or air [32], can enlarge the volume of pores in biochars, promoting
74 the formation of hierarchically porous structures at nano, micro, and macro scales (microporosity,
75 mesoporosity, macroporosity, respectively). In general, physical activation methods are also cheaper
76 and safer than chemical activation treatments involving high-temperature conditions with a
77 significant environmental footprint [29–31].

78 Herein, algal biomass, namely *Sargassum* brown macroalgae from Venice Lagoon, was used as a
79 biosource for the preparation of biochar. The widespread distribution of *Sargassum*, as well as the
80 bloom of other algae, in Venice Lagoon results from the eutrophication of the lagoon, *i.e.*, enrichment
81 of N- and P-rich nutrients, associated to the morphological and hydrodynamic setting of the lagoon.
82 The blooms of macroalgae and their subsequent decomposition have been typically associated to
83 negative effects, *i.e.*, anoxia in large parts of the Venice lagoon that causes mass mortality of benthic
84 animals and fish, coral reef destruction and toxin release [33]. Thus, the use of algae for the
85 preparation of biochar as a precursor of SC active materials can be considered as an environmentally
86 friendly approach to produce valuable products, while restoring and/or safeguarding the balance of
87 marine ecosystem negatively affected by human economic activities. The localized graphitic order
88 and the textural properties of *Sargassum*-derived biochar were then modified by a physical activation
89 process using CO₂ as an activation agent [26]. The effect of functional groups on the electrochemical
90 performance of the N, O, S-self-doped-activated biochar derived from *Sargassum* (ABS) was
91 investigated in SCs based on various types of electrolytes, including prototypical organic (1 M
92 tetraethylammonium tetrafluoroborate -TEABF₄- in acetonitrile -ACN-) and aqueous (1 M H₂SO₄
93 and 8 M NaNO₃) ones, reaching specific energies (Es) up to 12.4 Wh kg⁻¹ at 57.4 W kg⁻¹, 3.45 Wh
94 kg⁻¹ at 22.5 W kg⁻¹, and 6.35 Wh kg⁻¹ at 36.1 W kg⁻¹, respectively. Furthermore, flexible solid-state
95 SC (FSSSC) was also constructed by combining the designed ABS-based electrodes with a solid-
96 state electrolyte (SSE), namely a sulfonated polyether ether ketone (SPEEK):functionalized niobium
97 disulfide flakes (f-NbS₂) composite membrane developed in ref. [34]. The as-produced FSSC
98 exhibited an Es of 5.8 Wh kg⁻¹ at 87.4 W kg⁻¹, retaining its performance after several bending cycles
99 (up to 1000 cycles) and during folding conditions. The validation of ABS in different SC
100 configurations opens the way toward sustainable use of marine biomasses for electrochemical energy
101 storage applications.

102 2. Results and discussion

103 Scheme 1 represents the synthesis and activation method used to produce ABS (see details in
104 Supporting Information).

105 **Scheme 1.** Production of ABS through the activation of *Sargassum* brown macroalgae-derived
106 biochar.

107 Fig. 1a reports the Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectrum of ABS, showing the
108 presence of various functional groups. The band at around 3400 cm^{-1} is associated with hydroxyl
109 group vibrations [35]. The band at 1600 cm^{-1} is related to the stretching vibration of aromatic C=C
110 and stretching of C=O from conjugated ketones and quinones [36]. Moreover, a wide peak in the
111 range of $1400\text{-}900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is a series of overlapping bands likely ascribed to O-, N-, S-based dopants
112 and functional groups in ABS, including C–O bonds in phenol, alcohol, bridging ether between
113 aromatic rings, N–COO and N–C groups, S–O in sulfonate, S=O in sulfuric acid, SO₂ in sulfonic acid
114 and sulfone, respectively [37]. The bands at 2850 , 2920 , and 800 cm^{-1} are associated with aliphatic

115 (alkenes) and aromatic C–H, respectively [38]. Fig. 1b shows the X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern
116 measured for the ABS. This pattern exhibits two prominent peaks at 2θ values of approximately 25°
117 and 44° , corresponding to the (002) and (100) reflections of a disordered turbostratic carbon (or hard
118 carbon) structure, respectively [39]. In particular, according to Bragg's law [26], the interlayer
119 distance between the graphitic layers (d_{002}) of ABS is calculated to be ~ 0.357 nm, which is larger
120 than the d-spacing of graphite (0.335 nm) [40,41]. The increased interlayer spacing and the presence
121 of turbostratic disorder in ABS suggest enhanced electrochemical properties, including higher ion
122 accessibility and improved charge storage capabilities, which are beneficial for applications like SCs.
123 Fig. S1 presents the XRD pattern of the biochar, which behaves like disordered turbostratic carbon
124 structure. As for the activated counterpart, two broad diffraction peaks at 2θ values of approximately
125 23.5° and 43° correspond to the (002) and (100) reflections. The difference in the (002) peak positions
126 between the biochar and the ABS indicate different d_{002} , which is larger for the former (~ 0.378 nm).
127 In addition to the (002) and (100) reflections, several sharp peaks are present in the XRD patterns.
128 Notably, the sharp peak at 27° can be ascribed to some inorganic phases including crystalline SiO_2
129 (quartz (ICSD 83849), and Tridymite (ICSD 176)), typical contaminations present in quartz reactors
130 which cannot be removed during the HCl acid-washing step [26].”

131 Raman spectroscopy analysis was also performed to elucidate the structural order of ABS. The Raman
132 spectrum of ABS (Fig. 1C) exhibits distinct bands. The D band, located around 1360 cm^{-1} , is
133 associated with defects in graphitic structure and disorder, while the G band around 1600 cm^{-1}
134 corresponds to the graphitic layers and shows in-plane vibrational mode of sp^2 -hybridized carbon
135 atoms [42,43]. The band at *ca.* 2650 cm^{-1} is the overtone of D band and is denoted as 2D [44]. Lastly,
136 the band peaked at *ca.* 2950 cm^{-1} is associated with a D + G combination mode [45]. The ratio between
137 the intensity of D-band and G-band (I_D/I_G) was used to evaluate the degree of graphitization [43,46].
138 In this study, the I_D/I_G value is approximately 0.86. This ratio closely resembles values reported for
139 other activated biochars in literature [36,47].

140 Fig. 1d reports the N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherm measured for the ABS. A combination of type
141 I and type IV isotherms indicates the presence of a hierarchical micro-mesoporous texture. In
142 particular, the initial uptake of volume adsorbed at $P/P_0 < 0.2$ suggests the presence of micropores,
143 while the hysteresis loop at $0.4 < P/P_0 < 0.99$ is associated with the existence of narrow slit-shaped
144 mesopores (see Fig. S2 for pore size distribution). Similar results were obtained for activated biochars
145 produced by pyrolysis and physical activation (H₂O, H₂O/CO₂ as the activation agents) of *Sargassum*
146 [30]. Table 1 reports the textural properties of ABS including BET specific surface area (S_{BET})
147 calculated by BET method for multilayer adsorption considering interactions between adsorbed
148 molecules (N₂) within each layer. Additionally, it includes the Langmuir specific surface area
149 (S_{Langmuir}), determined by the Langmuir method for monolayer adsorption, where no interaction
150 among adsorbed molecules is considered, and the specific micropore surface area (S_{micro}), calculated
151 using the t-plot method. Notably, ABS exhibits a substantial S_{BET} of 821 m² g⁻¹, S_{Langmuir} of 1305 m²
152 g⁻¹, and S_{micro} of 905 m² g⁻¹, indicative of a hierarchical micro-mesoporous texture characterized by a
153 specific micropore volume (V_{micro}) of 0.17 cm³ g⁻¹, constituting 30% of the total pore volume ($V_{\text{tot}} =$
154 0.56 cm³ g⁻¹). Remarkable specific surfaces areas and mesoporosity ($V_{\text{meso}} = 0.39$ cm³ g⁻¹, mean pore
155 diameter (d_p) = 4.9 nm) of ABS are attributed to both the characteristics of the native *Sargassum*
156 biomass and its activation treatment. Importantly, ABS exhibits superior specific surface area and
157 mesoporosity compared to other biochars derived from various biomasses (including leather tannery
158 waste, barley waste, and vine wood waste) and activated like our ABS [48]. The distinctive textural
159 properties of ABS can therefore be associated with the peculiar composition of *Sargassum* biomass,
160 which is notably rich in proteins and lipids. During the thermal carbonization process under inert
161 atmosphere, biomasses release heteroatoms from their macromolecules' backbones, evolving into
162 porous carbon skeletons [49]. Subsequent activation processes further refine these structures,
163 resulting in a conductive 3D frameworks with hierarchical porosity and high specific surface area
164 suitable for SC applications [36,49]. It is well-documented that high-specific surface area carbons
165 featuring hierarchical pores provide abundant sites for electrolyte ions adsorption and infiltration,

166 facilitating rapid ion transport and diffusion during discharge/charge processes [18,50]. In particular,
167 micropores ensure high specific surface area which result in high capacitance, while the presence of
168 mesopores minimizes ion diffusion distance to achieve high rate capability [18,51].

169 Fig. 1e-f shows the transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of the ABS, revealing a porous
170 structure, as confirmed by gas physisorption measurements. Although the biochar mineral skeleton
171 is preserved, some mass is lost during the activation process, leading to enhanced porosity.

172 **Fig. 1.** Structural and morphological characterization of ABS. (a) FTIR spectra, (b) XRD pattern, and
173 (c) Raman spectrum measured for ABS. (d) N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms measured for
174 *Sargassum* brown macroalgae-derived biochar and ABS. TEM images of (e) ABS and (f) a magnified
175 area showing the material porous structure.

176 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were carried out to further evaluate the surface
177 morphology of ABS (Fig. 2). As shown in Fig. 2a, in some parts of its surface, the ABS shows a
178 beehive-like network made of pores and inner channels. A similar morphology has been observed for
179 biochars obtained from lignocellulosic biomasses due to the presence of carbohydrates [52], which
180 are also present in *Sargassum* brown macroalgae. Other parts of the ABS surface exhibit a rough and

181 irregular porous surface, leading to a heterogeneous morphology associated with the presence of high
 182 ash content in activated biomass-derived chars (Table S2).

183 **Table 1.** Textural properties of ABS obtained from N₂ physisorption measurements.

Sample	S _{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	S _{Langmuir} (m ² g ⁻¹)	S _{micro} (m ² g ⁻¹)	V _{tot} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	V _{micro} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	V _{meso} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	d _p (nm)
Activated biochar	821	1305	905	0.56	0.17	0.39	4.90

184

185 **Fig. 2.** (a) SEM images of ABS. (b) EDX spectrum and compositional analysis (inset table), and (c)
 186 the corresponding element maps of O, S, and N measured for ABS.

187 The dispersive energy X-ray (EDX) spectrum and element mapping of the ABS are shown in Fig. 2b-
 188 c, respectively, showing uniform element distributions. The compositional analysis (inset table to Fig.
 189 2b) and CHNS elemental analysis (Table S2) confirm the presence of O, N, and S heteroatoms, acting
 190 as dopants of forming functionalities in ABS obtained by carbohydrate-, protein- and lipid-containing
 191 *Sargassum*. Furthermore, Fig. S3 provides supplementary SEM-EDS analysis with a different

192 magnification, highlighting the presence and distribution of these elements, as well as C, P, and Si.
193 The surface chemical composition of the ABS was evaluated by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
194 (XPS) and the atomic ratios of C, O, N, and S (Table S3) were extracted from the wide scan XPS
195 spectrum (Fig. 3a). Silicon peaks are visible at approximately 100 and 150 eV and are attributed to
196 contamination in the sample, as often observed for materials activated in quartz reactors. Fig. 3b-e
197 reports the high-resolution N 1s, C 1s, S 2p, and O 1s XPS spectra. The N 1s spectrum (Fig. 3b) can
198 be deconvoluted into five peaks: pyridinic-N (398.2 ± 0.2 eV), amino/amide-N (399.5 ± 0.2 eV),
199 pyrrolic-N (400.1 ± 0.2 eV), quaternary-N (401.0 ± 0.2 eV), and oxidized-N (402.4 ± 0.3 eV) [53]. The
200 C 1s spectrum (Fig. 3c) is instead deconvoluted into seven peaks centered at (283.6 ± 0.2) eV,
201 (284.5 ± 0.2) eV, (284.8 ± 0.2) eV, (286.3 ± 0.2) eV, (287.8 ± 0.2) eV, (289.3 ± 0.2) eV, and (291.0 ± 0.2)
202 eV, corresponding to C vacancies, C=C (sp^2 -hybridized carbon), C-C (sp^3 -hybridized carbon), C-
203 O/C-OC and/or C=N linkage (phenolic hydroxyl/epoxy), C=O (carbonyl) and/or C-N and O=C-O
204 (carboxyl groups and/or ester groups), and π - π^* satellite peak, respectively [54]. In the S 2p spectrum
205 (Fig. 3d), two different doublets are associated with different chemical states, *i.e.*, thiol groups (S 2p
206 doublet with components peaking at 163.7 ± 0.2 for S $2p_{3/2}$ and 164.9 ± 0.2 eV for S $2p_{1/2}$) and sulfates
207 (S 2p doublet with components peaking at 167.7 ± 0.2 for S $2p_{3/2}$ and 168.9 ± 0.2 eV for S $2p_{1/2}$). These
208 two S chemical states have been respectively associated with the presence of the cysteine and sulfated
209 polysaccharides, as present in the *Sargassum* precursor [23]. Note that a Si plasmon loss peak is
210 present at (164.9 ± 0.2) eV and it has been considered in the deconvolution process. Lastly, the O 1s
211 spectrum (Fig. 3e) can be deconvoluted into four components corresponding to C=O (531.3 ± 0.2 eV),
212 S-O (532.3 ± 0.2 eV), O-C=O/-OH (532.9 ± 0.2 eV), and -COOH (534.7 ± 0.2 eV) groups [55]. The
213 presence of localized density of states (DOS) near the Fermi level has been documented [56,57] for
214 active materials containing pyridinic N, which may consequently improve the quantum capacitance
215 of undoped counterparts. More in details, this improvement arises from the increased availability of
216 electronic states for charge storage. The concentrated electronic states respond more efficiently to
217 changes in electrostatic potential, enhancing the material's ability to store electrical charge. This

218 heightened quantum capacitance is advantageous for applications like supercapacitors, in which rapid
 219 and responsive charge storage is crucial [58].

220 **Fig. 3.** (a) Wide scan XPS spectrum of the ABS. (b) N 1s, (c) C 1s, (d) S 2p, and (e) O 1s XPS spectra
 221 of the ABS.

222 In contrast, undoped counterparts lack the specific configurations that introduce these localized states,
223 resulting in less favorable electronic properties and a comparatively lower quantum capacitance
224 [57,59]. The concomitant presence of N and O is associated with the presence of defects and redox
225 active sites in carbonaceous active materials. Additionally, carbon atoms can function as Lewis bases
226 by donating electron pairs. The redox-active sites are typically associated with the carbon atoms
227 adjacent to pyridinic N, rather than the pyridinic N atoms themselves [60]. Like pyridinic N, sulfate
228 S exhibits electron-deficient characteristics, thereby promoting the formation of redox-active sites
229 involving conjoint carbon atoms for ion storage processes. In contrast, thiophene is considered an
230 electron-rich system with a weak ability to accept electrons [61]. Consequently, the carbon atoms
231 neighboring pyridinic N and sulfate S, possessing Lewis basicity, may play a crucial role in enhancing
232 electron transport and facilitating ion diffusion in SC electrodes [60]. Also, the surface activated
233 biochar is enriched with O, resulting in tunable hydrophilicity, regulating the wetting behavior and
234 ion transport [39]. In general, redox-active defective carbon sites can be transformed into ether or
235 carbonyl groups that also exhibit limited reactivity towards electrolyte decomposition reactions [62].

236 **Electrochemical characterization**

237 The ABS presented in this work has a unique structure of a three-dimensional carbon skeleton with a
238 large surface area of up to $821 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and hierarchical porosity combining micropores and mesopores.
239 These properties make the ABS a suitable active material for high-capacitance SC electrodes. In
240 addition, the interplay between electrode materials and electrolytes must be considered when
241 designing high-energy density SCs. In fact, the overall electrode capacitance depends on the
242 electrolyte ion accessibility to the surface of active materials. Meanwhile, the SC energy density
243 increases with the electrochemical stability window (ESW) of the electrolyte, whose reactivity is, in
244 turn, influenced by the electrode materials in contact with itself [63]. Different types of electrolytes,
245 including aqueous electrolytes, organic electrolytes, ionic liquids, and solid/quasi-solid-state
246 electrolytes, have been proposed for SCs, each with its advantages and disadvantages [64,65].

247 Aqueous electrolytes have advantages in terms of high ionic conductivity and environmental
248 friendliness compared with organic ones. However, their ESW is severely restricted by the oxygen
249 evolution reaction (OER) and hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) [66,67], thus limiting E_s , as well
250 as stability under accelerated aging tests (*e.g.*, voltage floating) [68]. Nevertheless, the formation of
251 hydrated solid phases or highly viscous aqueous solutions in highly concentrated electrolytes can
252 slow down the occurrence of irreversible water splitting reactions because of the reduced availability
253 of free-water molecules near the electrode surface [66,69]. Also, the low catalytic activity of
254 carbonaceous materials in near-neutral pH electrolytes (*e.g.*, NaNO_3 and other nitrates) [66],
255 attributed to the local acidification and basification at surfaces of the positive and negative electrode,
256 respectively, is an effective strategy to extend the device ESW beyond the thermodynamic voltage of
257 water splitting (*i.e.*, 1.23 V), even up to more than 2 V [66,69,70]. Of course, traditional organic
258 electrolytes, such as $\text{TEABF}_4/\text{ACN}$ and $\text{TEABF}_4/\text{polycarbonate (PC)}$, represent the robust benchmark
259 enabling SC operation up to voltage between 2.4-2.7 V, leading to E_s typically between 15-30 Wh
260 kg^{-1} , depending on the active material specifications [71]. Nonetheless, aqueous electrolytes still
261 represent a cost-effective solution (price of NaNO_3 is $<0.2 \text{ \$ g}^{-1}$, *versus* ca. $14.7 \text{ \$ g}^{-1}$ for TEABF_4)
262 [72,73], showing interesting properties in terms of ion conductivity (ranging from 10 to 100 mS cm^{-1})
263 ¹⁾ [72] and ion size (smaller than organic electrolyte ions) that ensure high-power density and high
264 capacitance performances, respectively [71]. Furthermore, SSEs have been developed to compensate
265 limitations associated with liquid electrolytes, including electrolyte leakage and excess weight. In this
266 context, polymeric SSEs provide outstanding mechanical stability, including bendability and
267 foldability, and eliminate concerns associated with leakage, flammability, and corrosivity of organic
268 electrolytes. These advantages, coupled with the potential for a more compact and denser design,
269 make SSEs particularly suitable for various applications in portable and wearable electronics,
270 including biomedical implants and health monitoring devices.

271 Based on these considerations, the ABS was evaluated as an active material for electrodes for EDLC-
272 type SCs based on representative aqueous and organic electrolytes, namely 1 M H_2SO_4 (acid) and 8

273 M NaNO₃ (near-neutral) aqueous electrolytes and 1 M TEABF₄/ACN, organic electrolyte. Also,
274 taking advantage of our previous work [34], the performance of the ABS active materials was
275 investigated in the presence of a SSE made of a SPEEK:f-NbS₂ composite membrane activated in 1
276 M H₂SO₄ and 8 M NaNO₃ solutions. In addition, as an alternative to polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF)
277 binder, SPEEK was screened as an ion-exchange polymeric binder in the presence of aqueous
278 electrolytes and SSE. The performances of ABS were also compared to those of a commercially
279 available AC. **Table 2** lists the details of the investigated SC configurations, including their
280 nomenclatures and indicating the working voltage window (WVW) used to measure their
281 performances.

282 Fig. 4a shows the CV curves measured for the ABS-based SCs, *i.e.*, ABS-H₂SO₄, ABS-NaNO₃, and
283 ABS-TEABF₄ at voltage scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹ and using WVWs of 1.0, 1.6, and 2.4 V, respectively.
284 The shapes of the CV curves are nearly rectangular, indicating capacitive behavior. Fig. S4a-c
285 illustrates CV curves measured for ABS-H₂SO₄, ABS-NaNO₃, and ABS-TEABF₄ electrodes at
286 various voltage scan rates, ranging from 5 to 1500 mV s⁻¹. The SC curves maintained their quasi-
287 rectangular shape with the increase of the voltage scan rate, indicating satisfactory rate capability.
288 Fig. 4b shows the galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) analysis of the ABS-H₂SO₄, ABS-NaNO₃,
289 and ABS-TEABF₄ electrodes at 0.5 A g⁻¹. The triangular GCD profiles confirm the capacitive
290 behavior of these devices. Fig. S4a-c reports the GCD profiles recorded for these devices at various
291 specific currents, ranging from 0.1 to 50 A g⁻¹, evidencing almost ideal capacitive behaviors, thus,
292 confirming CV results. Furthermore, CV and GCD analyses were performed on SCs based on
293 commercial AC as the active material, *i.e.*, AC-H₂SO₄ (ref.), AC-NaNO₃ (ref.), and AC-TEABF₄
294 (ref.), (Fig. S5a-c). Compared to ABS-based SCs, the specific currents and time discharges are
295 similar. Fig. 4c shows the electrode C_g measured for the ABS-based SCs as a function of the specific
296 current. At 0.1 A g⁻¹, ABS-H₂SO₄, ABS-NaNO₃, and ABS-TEABF₄ EDLCs achieved electrode C_g
297 of 109.5, 79.0 and 64.3 F g⁻¹, respectively.

298 **Table 2.** List of the investigated SC configurations and the AC-based EDLC (reference devices)
 299 using different electrolytes and binders including relevant performance metrics.

Active material	Binder	Separator/ SSE	Electrolyte	Acronym	WWW (V)	C_g (F g ⁻¹)	Es (Wh kg ⁻¹)
ABS	SPEEK	Glassy fiber (gf)	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	ABS-H ₂ SO ₄	1	109.5	3.4
ABS	SPEEK	gf	8 M NaNO ₃	ABS-NaNO ₃	1.6	79.0	6.3
ABS	PVDF	gf	1 M TEABF ₄ / ACN	ABS-TEABF ₄	2.4	64.3	12.4
ABS	SPEEK	SPEEK:f-NbS ₂		SSSC-H ₂ SO ₄	1	100.6	3.1
ABS	SPEEK	SPEEK:f-NbS ₂		SSSC-NaNO ₃	1.6	66.7	5.4
AC	SPEEK	gf	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	AC-H ₂ SO ₄ (ref.)	1	124.5	3.7
AC	SPEEK	gf	8 M NaNO ₃	AC-NaNO ₃ (ref.)	1.6	88.1	6.8
AC	PVDF	gf	1 M TEABF ₄ / ACN	AC-TEABF ₄ (ref.)	2.4	71.4	14.8

300

301 By increasing the specific current to 50 A g⁻¹, the C_g decreased to 78.6, 52.9, and 40.5 F g⁻¹, for ABS-
 302 H₂SO₄, ABS-NaNO₃, and ABS-TEABF₄ EDLCs, respectively. This reduction is a consequence of
 303 ohmic losses, including those associated with the ion diffusion within the pores of the ABS [74].
 304 Amongst the SC configurations, the differences in C_g can be attributed to the ionic radius and

305 conductivity of the electrolytes [75]. Table S4 reports the ionic and solvation sphere values for
306 different ions, revealing a trend for the solvated ion size: $H^+ < Na^+ < TEA^+$. Notably, H^+ ions exhibit
307 the highest molar ionic conductivity, while TEA^+ ions show the lowest one. Additionally, SO_4^{2-} ions
308 exhibit a molar ionic conductivity higher than that of BF_4^- ions [76]. According to the molecular ionic
309 conductivities, 1 M TEABF₄/ACN shows ionic conductivity in the range of 50-60 mS cm⁻¹ (e.g., 52.1
310 [77], and 60.0 [78] mS cm⁻¹), while 8 M NaNO₃ and 1 M H₂SO₄ exhibit higher ionic conductivity,
311 e.g., ~170 [69] and ~800 mS cm⁻¹ [79], respectively. In our ABS-based electrodes, the interplay
312 between ion size and mobility can significantly affect the overall capacitive performance. Differently
313 from the ABS-TEABF₄/ACN, the micropores in ABS-H₂SO₄ and ABS-NaNO₃ electrodes can
314 efficiently accommodate solvated ions, leading to outstanding C_g, especially for the 1 M H₂SO₄
315 electrolyte. The superior C_g of aqueous SCs compared to counterpart based on organic electrolytes is
316 a commonly observed behavior [80]. Compared to aqueous AC-based SCs, the superior capacitive
317 performance of the ABS-based SCs is attributed to their key structural characteristics. The porous
318 structure facilitates efficient charge and ion transport even into micropores, while mesopores act as
319 ion-buffering reservoirs [81,82]. The presence of heteroatom functional groups within ABS provides
320 additional sites for charge storage and promotes redox reactions, introducing a pseudocapacitance
321 contribution [83]. The electrode C_g (and specific capacities) measured for reference AC-based SCs
322 are reported in Fig. S6. Regarding the specific capacity (Fig. 4c, inset), ABS-TEABF₄ outperforms
323 ABS-H₂SO₄, and ABS-NaNO₃, since the former was evaluated in a larger WWV (i.e., 2.4 V). As
324 shown in Fig. S7a and b, the Coulombic efficiency (CE) of the investigated SCs is almost 100% at
325 high specific currents, i.e., >5 A g⁻¹. At lower current density, CE progressively decreases as a
326 consequence of parasitic reactions, which are more pronounced in the presence of aqueous
327 electrolytes, in particular in 1 M H₂SO₄ [66]. The energy efficiency (EE) remains in the range of 70
328 to 90% and exhibits a peak at moderate specific currents (from 1 to 2 A g⁻¹), reflecting efficient charge
329 storage without relevant ohmic losses associated with internal series resistances, which is higher in

330 ABS-TEABF₄ [84]. The CE and EE measured for the AC-based devices are reported in Fig. S8a-b,
 331 and their trends are similar to those of ABS-based SCs.

332

333 **Fig. 4.** Electrochemical characterization of the investigated ABS-based SCs in different electrolytes.

334 (a) CV curves, measured at 100 mV s⁻¹, and (b) GCD profiles, measured at 0.5 A g⁻¹, for ABS-H₂SO₄,

335 ABS-NaNO₃, and ABS-TEABF₄ SCs. (c) Electrode C_g (inset, specific capacity) measured for the

336 investigated ABS-based EDLCs as a function of the specific current (data extrapolated from the GCD

337 profiles). (d) Ragone plots, (e) C_g retention, and (f) CE over 10000 GCD cycles at 2 A g⁻¹ measured

338 for the investigated ABS-based SCs.

339 Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was carried out to evaluate the capacitive, resistive,
340 and charge transport characteristics of the investigated devices. As shown in Fig. S9, the Nyquist
341 plots in the low-frequency region display nearly vertical straight lines, which are indications of a
342 capacitive behavior. The slope deviation from 90° is associated with ion diffusion into electrode
343 material pore channels, as modeled by the so-called Warburg impedance (W) [85]. The intercept at
344 high frequency provides information on bulk electrolyte resistance (R_e), decreasing in the order of
345 $TEABF_4 > NaNO_3 > H_2SO_4$. These trends are consistent with the one of the ionic conductivities of
346 the electrolytes. The R_e values measured for ABS- H_2SO_4 , ABS- $NaNO_3$, and ABS- $TEABF_4$ electrodes
347 are 0.43, 0.66, and 0.87 Ω , respectively. The small semicircle in the high/frequency region of the
348 Nyquist plot represents the RC circuit given by the current collector/electrode interface[13], even
349 though it may include the impedance contribution associated with parasitic redox reactions. The
350 semicircle diameter denotes an overall charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) [86], which decreases in the
351 order of $ABS-H_2SO_4 < ABS-NaNO_3 < ABS-TEABF_4$. This behavior is likely associated with the
352 presence of parasitic water splitting reactions, which are more pronounced in acid aqueous
353 electrolytes compared to the other cases, as discussed in ref. [66].

354 Fig. 4d displays the Ragone plot (*i.e.*, E_s vs. P_s) of the ABS-based SCs, as derived from their GCD
355 analysis. As expected by its largest WVW, ABS- $TEABF_4$ exhibited the highest E_s , achieving 12.4
356 $Wh\ kg^{-1}$ at $57.4\ W\ kg^{-1}$ and $24.5\ kW\ kg^{-1}$ at $6.6\ Wh\ kg^{-1}$. In the neutral and acidic aqueous electrolytes,
357 the devices reached E_s of $6.3\ Wh\ kg^{-1}$ at $36.1\ W\ kg^{-1}$ and $3.4\ Wh\ kg^{-1}$ at $22.5\ W\ kg^{-1}$, respectively.
358 Fig. S10 shows the Ragone plots measured for the AC-based SCs. The AC- H_2SO_4 (ref.), AC- $NaNO_3$
359 (ref.), and AC- $TEABF_4$ (ref.) achieved E_s of $3.7\ Wh\ kg^{-1}$ at $21.7\ W\ kg^{-1}$, $6.8\ Wh\ kg^{-1}$ at $34.8\ W\ kg^{-1}$,
360 and $14.8\ Wh\ kg^{-1}$ at $62.2\ W\ kg^{-1}$, respectively. Furthermore, equivalent series resistance (ESR) and
361 maximum specific power (P_{max}), were calculated according to equations S6 and S7. The calculated
362 ESR values are 1.3, 1.0, and 0.61 Ω for ABS- $TEABF_4$, ABS- $NaNO_3$ and ABS- H_2SO_4 , respectively.
363 These ESR values correspond to P_{max} of 378, 222, and 147 $kW\ kg^{-1}$, respectively. Noteworthy, ESR
364 depends on the electrolyte ionic conductivity as well as by other resistance contribution associated

365 with either transport of the electrolyte within the porous electrodes or current collector/electrode film
366 interfaces. Meanwhile, P_{\max} is inversely proportional to the ESR but is also proportional to the square
367 of the WWV. Consequently, even though ABS-TEABF₄ exhibits the highest ESR amongst the
368 investigated devices with liquid electrolyte (see Fig. S9 and Table S4), it achieves the highest P_{\max}
369 (378 kW kg⁻¹) owing to its larger WWV (*i.e.*, 2.4 V). Despite the ABS-H₂SO₄ exhibits the lowest
370 ESR (0.61 Ω), its limited WWV (1 V) also leads to the lowest P_{\max} of 147 kW kg⁻¹.

371 In general, ABS and AC resulted in similar performances, regardless of electrolytes. Nevertheless,
372 thanks to the sustainability of its precursors, ABS may represent a sustainable alternative to common
373 ACs produced from non-renewable resources. The long-term cyclic stability of ABS-based SCs was
374 assessed over 10000 GCD cycles at a current density of 2 A g⁻¹. As shown in Fig. 4e, the cyclic
375 stability of aqueous SCs surpassed that obtained with organic electrolytes. Particularly, ABS-H₂SO₄
376 retained 99.6% of its C_g . In contrast, ABS-TEABF₄ exhibited a C_g retention of 88%. Nevertheless,
377 strategies, for example, concerning the optimization of the electrode mass ratio can be prospectively
378 used to minimize the degradation rate of devices based on organic electrolytes [87]. The investigated
379 devices maintained a CE exceeding 98% at the end of the stability test (Fig. 4f), indicating satisfactory
380 reversibility over cycling. Table S5 compares the performance of ABS-based SCs with those
381 obtained with biomass/derived active materials reported in the literature.

382 Furthermore, Fig. 5 shows the results obtained for SSSC-H₂SO₄, and SSSC-NaNO₃ solid-state SCs
383 (SSSCs), assembled with the SPEEK:f-NbS₂ composite membranes (activated in 1 M H₂SO₄ and 8
384 M NaNO₃, respectively) as SSEs. Fig. 5a reports the CV curves measured for SSSC-H₂SO₄ and
385 SSSC-NaNO₃ at the voltage scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹, indicating the capacitive behavior of the devices,
386 as also associated with the effective ion transport of the SSEs. Compared to the SSSC-NaNO₃ case,
387 the higher specific currents measured for SSSC-H₂SO₄ reflects the superior H⁺ conductivity
388 compared to Na⁺ in ion-exchanging polymeric membranes [88,89]. Fig. 5b shows the GCD analysis
389 for both devices at a specific current of 0.5 A g⁻¹, confirming a nearly capacitive behavior. The CV

390 data acquired for the SSCs at various voltage scan rates, ranging from 5 to 1500 mV s⁻¹, are shown
391 in Fig. S11a-b. By increasing the voltage scan rate in SSSC-NaNO₃, a slight deformation of the
392 rectangular CV shape suggests an inferior rate capability compared to that of SSSC-H₂SO₄ [90].

393 Fig. S11c-d depict the GCD profiles measured for SSSC-H₂SO₄ and SSSC-NaNO₃ at various specific
394 currents, ranging from 0.1 to 50 A g⁻¹. These data confirm the superior rate capability of SSSC-H₂SO₄
395 compared to SSSC-NaNO₃, because of the different ion transport abilities of the SSEs. In our specific
396 SSEs, the ion transport ability results from the interactions of sulfuric acid functional groups in
397 polymeric chains and f-SNbS₂ nanosheets with cations (*i.e.*, H⁺ and Na⁺) [91]. Thus, in SSSC-H₂SO₄,
398 sulfuric acid groups enhance H⁺ ion transport, benefiting from their small size and high mobility,
399 leading to excellent ion conductivity (*i.e.*, ~94 mS cm⁻¹) [34]. Fig. 5c displays the C_g and specific
400 capacity measured for SSSC-H₂SO₄ and SSSC-NaNO₃ as a function of the specific current, from 0.1
401 to 50 A g⁻¹. The C_g decreases from 100.6 F g⁻¹ to 74.9 F g⁻¹ for SSSC-H₂SO₄ (74.4% C_g retention)
402 and from 66.7 F g⁻¹ to 35.3 F g⁻¹ for SSSC-NaNO₃ (53.2% C_g retention) as the specific current
403 increases from 0.1 to 50 A g⁻¹, remarking the excellent rate capability of SSSC-H₂SO₄. Fig. S12a-b
404 illustrates the CE and EE obtained for SSSC-H₂SO₄ and SSSC-NaNO₃ as a function of the specific
405 current. SSSC-NaNO₃ shows a CE of 79% at 0.1 A g⁻¹, indicating the presence of current leakage at
406 the electrode-electrolyte interface due to parasitic electrochemical reactions. The latter may be
407 reduced by lowering the WVW to less than 1.4 V. In this case, the insufficient Na⁺ transport in SSE
408 may also results in a poor balance of the electrode capacities, limiting the WVW to lower values
409 compared to the aqueous SC based on 8 M NaNO₃. Conversely, at 0.1 A g⁻¹, SSSC-H₂SO₄ still
410 exhibited a CE as high as 93%, indicating the possibility of reducing parasitic reaction compared to
411 the aqueous SC using 1 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte [92]. In terms of EE, SSSC-H₂SO₄ outperformed SSSC-
412 NaNO₃ and reached EEs of 75.8% and 63.2% at 0.1 and 50 A g⁻¹, respectively. Fig. S13 shows the
413 EIS analysis of SSCs, indicating that SSSC-H₂SO₄ has an R_s value of 0.78 Ω, lower than the one of
414 SSSC-NaNO₃ (1.0 Ω). Also, SSSC-NaNO₃ exhibited a R_{ct} of 1.9 Ω, which is higher than the one of

415 SSSC-H₂SO₄ (0.34 Ω), in agreement with the EE trends of these devices. Fig. 5d presents the Ragone
 416 plots of the SSSCs, showing that SSSC-H₂SO₄ achieved a maximum Es of 3.1 Wh kg⁻¹ at 21.8 W kg⁻¹
 417 ¹ and a maximum Ps of 10 kW kg⁻¹ at 2.1 Wh kg⁻¹, while SSSC-NaNO₃ reached a maximum Es of
 418 5.4 Wh kg⁻¹ at 36.7 W kg⁻¹ and a maximum Ps of 11.3 kW kg⁻¹ at 1.8 Wh kg⁻¹.

419
 420 **Fig. 5.** Electrochemical characterization of the investigated SSSCs. (a) CV curves, measured at 100
 421 mV s⁻¹, (b) GCD profiles, measured at 0.5 A g⁻¹, for SSSC-H₂SO₄ and SSSC-NaNO₃ SCs. (c)
 422 Electrode C_g (inset, specific capacity) measured for the investigated SSSCs as a function of the
 423 specific current (data extrapolated from the GCD analysis). (d) Ragone plots, (e) C_g retention, and (f)
 424 CE over 10000 GCD cycles at 2 A g⁻¹ measured for the investigated SSSCs.

425 SSSC-NaNO₃ exhibits higher P_{max} (88 kW kg⁻¹) despite its higher ESR (2.6 Ω) than SSSC-H₂SO₄
426 (P_{max} of 54 kW kg⁻¹ and ESR of 1.6 Ω). Additionally, Fig. 5e-f reveal the cyclic stability of SSSC-
427 H₂SO₄ and SSSC-NaNO₃. After 10000 GCD cycles at 2 A g⁻¹, SSSC-H₂SO₄ retained 96.7% and
428 99.0% of its C_g and CE, respectively. These results emphasize the excellent cyclability of SSSC-
429 H₂SO₄, superior to that of its aqueous analogous. Fig. S14 shows the Raman analysis of ABS-based
430 electrodes after 10000 GCD cycles to evaluate the impact of electrolytes and the GCD cycling on
431 their structure. In fact, the analysis of the I_D/I_G ratio can reflect the evolution of the structural
432 characteristics of the electrodes before and after cyclic stability analysis [27,93]. As shown in Fig.
433 S14b, the pristine electrode exhibits an initial I_D/I_G ratio of approximately 0.88. For all the samples
434 except ABS-TEABF₄, the I_D/I_G ratio has shown non-relevant changes after 10000 GCD cycles,
435 indicating that the electrodes maintained their structural and morphological integrity during cycling.
436 In contrast, ABS-TEABF₄ undergoes substantial structural changes, likely explaining the C_g fade
437 during GCD cycling (see Fig. S4c).

438 Table 2 provides a comparison between C_g and Es measured for the investigated devices. Also, Fig.
439 6a-b serves as a visual (qualitative) aid for comparing the performances (expressed in scorecards) of
440 the ABS-based SCs, distinguished on the basis of their electrolyte, covering five key metrics: C_g,
441 specific capacity, maximum achieved Es, Pmax, and cyclic stability after 10000 GCD cycles. These
442 key parameters are categorized into five levels (ranging from 1 to 5), with higher values signifying a
443 more favorable impact of the electrolytes on the performance metrics of ABS-based SCs. The H₂SO₄-
444 based results in better C_g than other samples due to the small size of solvated H⁺. Conversely,
445 TEABF₄/ACN limits the C_g due to the large size of its solvated ions (TEA⁺ and BF₄⁻), impeding
446 effective access into the microporosities of the ABS. In terms of Es, TEABF₄/ACN and NaNO₃-based
447 electrolytes provide clear benefits thanks to their larger WWV compared to that of H₂SO₄-based
448 electrolytes. Cycling stability is given by aqueous electrolytes, particularly H₂SO₄-based ones, while
449 TEABF₄/ACN may cause mechanical stresses associated with the large size of its solvated ions.
450 Furthermore, ABS-TEABF₄ SC exhibits the highest P_{max} despite its highest ESR, emphasizing the

451 dominant effect of the WVW on the performance of the SCs. Fig. 6b shows the scorecards assigned
452 to SSSCs. Compared to SSSC-NaNO₃, SSSC-H₂SO₄ offers higher C_g and cyclic stability but lower
453 P_{max} and Es.

454

455 **Fig. 6.** Comparative analysis, qualitatively expressed in form of scorecards, of the key metrics of SCs
456 based on (a) liquid electrolytes, *i.e.*, 1 M H₂SO₄, 8 M NaNO₃, and 1 M TEABF₄/ACN and (b) SSEs.

457 To fulfill practical demands, ABS-based FSSSC were assembled and characterized upon applying
458 mechanical stresses. Based on the previous electrochemical characterization, SSSC-H₂SO₄ was
459 selected to assemble our FSSSC, as depicted in Fig. 7. The active area of the device was 1.2 cm×1.6
460 cm, obtained by sandwiching a SPEEK-2.5%-f-NbS₂:SPEEK composite SSE, activated in 1 M
461 H₂SO₄, between two ABS-based electrodes deposited on flexible carbon cloths, serving as current
462 collectors. Fig.7a reports the CV curves measured for the FSSSC at various voltage scan rates,
463 ranging from 5 to 400 mV s⁻¹. The rectangular shape of the CV curves indicates the capacitive
464 behavior of the device, as also confirmed by the triangular shape of its GCD profiles (Fig. 7b). As
465 shown in Fig.7c, the FSSSC exhibited a satisfactory rate capability, retaining 72% of its C_g measured
466 at 0.1 A g⁻¹ when tested at the highest specific current of 10 A g⁻¹. After subsequent bending cycles
467 (250, 500, 750, and 1000) at 1 A g⁻¹, the FSSSC optimally retained its C_g and CE (Fig.7d). In
468 particular, the FSSSC retained 97% of C_g and 98% of CE after 1000 bending cycles at a curvature
469 radius of 2 cm (Fig.7e), demonstrating remarkable flexibility. The performances of the device were
470 also examined under 60°, 120°, and 180° folding angles, demonstrating excellent folding resistance.

471 As shown in Fig.7f, the FSSSC retained >95% of its C_g for all the folding conditions. The remarkable
 472 mechanical stability of the FSSSC during bending and folding is attributed to the unique mechanical
 473 properties of the optimized composite SSE, 2.5%-f-NbS₂:SPEEK, the mechanical robustness of the
 474 ABS-based electrodes and the flexibility of carbon cloth current collectors.

475

476 **Fig.7.** Electrochemical characterization of the ABS-based FSSSC. (a) CV curves measured at
 477 different voltage scan rates, ranging from 5 to 400 mV s⁻¹, (b) GCD profiles measured at various
 478 specific currents, ranging from 0.1 to 10 A g⁻¹. (c) C_g and CE as function of the specific current. (d)
 479 GCD profiles measured after 250, 500, 750, and 1000 bending cycles at 1 A g⁻¹ (curvature radius = 2
 480 cm). (e) C_g retention and CE of the FSSSC over 1000 bending cycles. (f) C_g retention and CE of the
 481 FSSSC folded at 0°, 60°, 120°, and 180°.

482 **3. Conclusion**

483 This study has successfully demonstrated a sustainable and high-performance electrode active
484 material for supercapacitors (SCs) derived from Venice lagoon's Sargassum brown macroalgae. A
485 self-doped porous activated biochar (ABS) was produced exploiting a straightforward
486 thermochemical process, followed by CO₂ activation. The electrochemical characterization of ABS-
487 based SCs in various electrolytes, including aqueous (1 M H₂SO₄, and 8 M NaNO₃), organic (1 M
488 TEABF₄/ACN), and solid-state electrolytes (SSEs) sulfonated poly ether ether ketone: functionalized
489 niobium disulfide flakes (SPEEK: f-NbS₂) composites, demonstrates promising capacitive
490 performances in terms of C_g, energy/power densities, efficiency, and cyclic stability. With liquid
491 electrolytes, ABS-based SCs achieved energy densities of 3.4 Wh kg⁻¹ at 22.5 W kg⁻¹, 6.3 Wh kg⁻¹ at
492 36.1 W kg⁻¹, and 12.4 Wh kg⁻¹ at 57.4 W kg⁻¹, and maximum power densities of 147-, 222-, and 378-
493 kW kg⁻¹, in the acidic, quasi-neutral aqueous electrolyte and organic electrolyte, respectively.
494 Furthermore, after evaluating the electrochemical performance of the ABS-based electrodes in solid-
495 state supercapacitor, a flexible solid-state supercapacitor (FSSSC) was fabricated based on ABS-
496 electrode and SPEEK:f-NbS₂ SSE. Our FSSSC stably operated under mechanical stress, including
497 bending up to 1000 times and folding angles up to 180°, retaining more than 95% of its initial C_g. The
498 outstanding performance of ABS-based SCs is attributed to its pore distribution, heteroatom doping,
499 and improved surface characteristics. These features synergistically create abundant active sites for
500 charge accumulation, promote effective electrolyte diffusion, and elevate electrochemical activity.
501 These findings highlight the considerable potential of ABS as an environmentally friendly and high-
502 performance alternative to conventional activated carbon for SCs and other energy storage
503 applications.

504 **4. Experimental Section**

505 Detailed information related to the preparation of activated biochar derived from Sargassum,
506 electrodes and electrolytes preparation, physicochemical characterization, and electrochemical

507 evaluation of ABS-based electrodes for supercapacitor application is provided in Supporting
508 Information.

509 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

510 **Ahmad Bagheri:** Writing original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

511 **Somayeh Taghavi:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing-review & editing. **Sebastiano Bellani:**

512 Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Writing-review & editing. **Pejman**

513 **Salimi:** Formal analysis curation, Writing-review & editing. **Hossein Beydaghi:** Methodology,

514 Investigation, Validation, Writing-review & editing. **Jaya-Kumar Panda:** Methodology,

515 Investigation. **Marilena Isabella Zappia:** Methodology, Investigation. **Valentina Mastronardi:**

516 Methodology, Investigation. **Agnese Gamberini:** Methodology. **Sanjay Thorat:** Methodology.

517 **Matteo Abruzzese:** Methodology. **Lea Pasquale:** Methodology, Investigation. **Mirko Prato:**

518 Methodology, Investigation. **Michela Signoretto:** Supervision, Writing-review & editing. **Xinliang**

519 **Feng:** Supervision, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Francesco Bonaccorso:** Writing-

520 review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization

521 **Conflict of Interest**

522 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships

523 that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. A. Bagheri, S. Bellani, H.

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525 and F. Bonaccorso are employees of BeDimensional S.p.A., a company producing two-dimensional

526 materials.

527 **Data availability**

528 Data will be made available on request.

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539 **Supporting Information**

540 Supplementary material associated with this article can be found in the online version.

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